

Principles for fair, equitable and productive international collaborations

The principles are based on practical experiences from 13 research projects and were collectively developed during the “Sustainability and Resilience – Tackling consequences of climate and environmental changes” closing seminar on May 24th-25th, 2023 at the Stockholm Resilience Centre, Stockholm University, Sweden.

STAGE 1. Developing the proposal and seeking/obtaining funding e.g., deciding on research topics, potential research partners, collaborators, research methods.

- Effective leadership along with an open dialogue and honest communication.
- Involvement in the research including mobilization, cultural sensitivity and local perspectives.
- Participation that entails team building while setting mutual expectations and a safe atmosphere. Be clear and explicit about expectation and motivations.
- Flexible planning with a clear timeline, detailed schedule and milestones.
- Sharing of responsibilities within a respectful environment.
- Consolidation of a research proposal for funding that is collaboratively developed.

STAGE 2. Startup of the research e.g., recruiting, initiating contact with communities and stakeholders, among others.

- Organize a kick off meeting: discuss the principles, bring everyone together, reassess the research proposal, create spaces to build trust and empathy.
- Clear distribution of roles, responsibilities and tasks in an open and transparent way.
- Assess the community's norms and values and reflect about access.
- Understand the local context and refine the project activities accordingly.
- When contacting communities and other stakeholders, be genuine, humble, and remember to respect differences.
- Communicate and disseminate at every stage of the project within the team and with participants.

STAGE 3. On-going research e.g., data collection, sharing field data/input data, analysis phase and managing relationships with stakeholders, economic bureaucracy, receipts, bookings, per diems, etc.

- Regular follow-ups and one-on-one meetings with active listening and participation.
- Foster a culture of openness and honesty about conflict of interest, challenges and limitations, where everyone can share difficulties, ask for help and better understand why they are not delivering.
- Budget for contingencies or emerging opportunities either within the project budgets or available as top-up/continuation grants.
- Take time for pre-fieldwork, piloting, testing, explaining the project and making field contacts – all need to understand the research and talk about ownership.
- Communicate timely about emerging problems.
- Foster interdisciplinary approaches. Be open to methodological feedback from the field (be adaptive) and have regular debrief sessions where principal investigators are also present.
- Ensure continuous learning and capacity building at all levels and stages (principal investigators, team members, field workers) - Build long term capacitated teams.
- Be responsible, transparent and accountable regarding project economy, resources and data.

Background. The four stages and recommendations are a co-produced effort of all the participants at the SaR closing seminar, and are further described in the report *Fair, equitable and productive international collaborative research: experiences from 13 research projects* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10254516>) please read the report for more details on the principles and how they were developed.

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STAGE 4. Closing phase - final stages e.g., publishing, writing articles, reports to funders and others, handling co-authorships, and disseminating the results etc.

- Clear mutual agreements between project participants with respect to project products, milestones and timeline.
- Promote transparency and openness in all activities and project components including budget, authorship, data collection, delays, etc.
- Strategic planning including a clear roadmap (timeline) with milestones on budget, publications and other outputs (various stages, submission). Keep communication going at all levels.
- Work together to reach the milestones (co-production), ask for help and admit struggles, listen to each other, express expectations and remember to provide positive feedback.
- Principal investigators and collaborators should especially be aware and understand the large amount of time and energy needed to navigate admin and financial systems.

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The checklist is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10371680>